

PRISM - An Agentic RAG-Based Platform for Competitive Examination Preparation with Personalized Learning and Real-Time Collaboration

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Abstract—Students preparing for competitive examinations such as JEE Mains, JEE Advanced, and NEET face a persistent challenge: study resources are fragmented across dozens of platforms, AI tools hallucinate answers not grounded in verified syllabus content, and no single environment supports integrated doubt resolution, practice, and peer collaboration. This paper presents PRISM, an intelligent examination preparation platform built on an Agentic Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) pipeline implemented using LangGraph, LangChain, FAISS, and the Ollama llama3.2 language model. The system indexes 19,776 vector embeddings derived from 40+ NCERT textbooks, previous year question (PYQ) papers, and supplementary reference materials using the all-MiniLM-L6-v2 sentence transformer. A five-node agentic pipeline — Router, Retrieve, Grade, Rewrite, Generate — ensures domain-accurate responses grounded exclusively in indexed academic sources. Beyond the RAG agent, PRISM integrates a PYQ-mode quiz engine, NCERT line-by-line reading with global content caching, real-time competitive battle rooms via Socket.IO, adaptive study planning, and a cross-device leaderboard stored in MongoDB Atlas. Evaluation shows consistent retrieval of subject-relevant content within 3–5 seconds per query on commodity hardware without cloud API dependency.

Keywords— Index Terms—Retrieval-Augmented Generation, LangGraph, FAISS, Ollama, Competitive Examination Preparation, Personalized Learning, Socket.IO, Real-Time Systems, Natural Language Processing, EdTech.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Joint Entrance Examination (JEE) and National Eligibility cum Entrance Test (NEET) are among the most competitive examinations in India, with over 3 million candidates appearing annually [3][4]. These examinations draw heavily from NCERT textbook content — particularly in Chemistry and Biology — where questions are often derived verbatim from specific lines in the prescribed curriculum. Despite widespread access to digital learning platforms, students continue to struggle with three persistent problems: resource fragmentation across multiple applications, unreliable AI-generated answers not grounded in verified academic sources, and absence of a collaborative peer study environment within a focused academic context. Online education has grown quickly, giving students access to coaching apps, video lessons, and shared notes. Still, the large number of options often leads to confusion rather than clarity, making students spend more time searching than studying. Platforms such as BYJU'S and Unacademy offer structured video content but do not dynamically respond to individual student queries or adapt to specific weak areas [5][6]. General-purpose large language models such as ChatGPT can produce fluent explanations but are known to hallucinate factually incorrect information — a critical failure mode in high-stakes examination preparation where accuracy of a single formula or reaction mechanism can determine a student's score [8]. The Retrieval - Augmented Generation (RAG) paradigm, introduced by Lewis et al. [17], addresses this by constraining generation to a verified document corpus, ensuring that responses are grounded in indexed source material.

Recent AI-based conversational tools can provide answers almost instantly. Unfortunately, they do not always rely on verified academic sources, leading to worries about their reliability for high-stakes exam preparation. Therefore, there is a strong need for a platform that combines accurate information retrieval with smart response generation while keeping academic correctness.

This paper introduces PRISM (Personalized Resource and Intelligent Study Monitor), an integrated examination preparation platform that implements an agentic five-node RAG pipeline using LangGraph [16]. Unlike single-step RAG systems, PRISM's pipeline incorporates explicit query routing, document relevance grading, and query rewriting — improving retrieval precision on domain-specific academic queries. The system indexes content from over 40 academic PDFs into a FAISS vector store [20] containing 19,776 embeddings, enabling millisecond-speed semantic retrieval without cloud dependency. The platform is deployable on a local machine or edge device, requiring no paid API subscriptions. The system uses standard study materials like NCERT textbooks and past exam papers, converting them into vector embeddings. This allows it to extract conceptually relevant information for any user query.

When a student asks a question, the assistant pulls matching content from its internal database and crafts a response that is both informative and based on verified sources. This approach improves the overall quality of learning. In addition to answering questions, the system helps learners by creating customized study schedules, designing topic-specific quizzes, and offering guidance based on subject importance and exam patterns, leading to more organized preparation.

The primary contributions of this paper are: (1) an agentic five-node LangGraph pipeline for domain-constrained question answering; (2) a three-tier PDF ingestion pipeline with OCR fallback for scanned document processing; (3) a real-time competitive quiz system using Socket.IO with synchronized timers across distributed clients; (4) a globally cached NCERT content generation system where content generated by any user is permanently available to all users without re-generation; and (5) a cross-device leaderboard backed by MongoDB Atlas integrating scores from all platform features.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Digital platforms have significantly transformed examination preparation in India. Structured e-learning systems provide video-based content delivery organized around prescribed syllabi, giving students asynchronous access to recorded lectures [5][6]. However, such systems are fundamentally passive — they broadcast content uniformly without adapting to a student's demonstrated knowledge gaps or responding to specific academic queries in real time.

The integration of natural language processing into education has been explored through various approaches. Adaptive tutoring systems use student response histories to modify the difficulty and topic selection of subsequent content [17]. Recommendation systems have been applied to suggest study resources based on behavioral patterns. However, these systems typically operate on curated metadata rather than full document content, limiting their ability to answer open-ended concept questions.

The emergence of large language models (LLMs) such as GPT series models has demonstrated remarkable fluency in question answering [8]. However, LLMs trained on general web corpora are known to generate plausible but factually incorrect information — a phenomenon termed hallucination — which is particularly damaging in examination contexts where precision of chemical formulas, biological processes, and mathematical derivations is critical. This limitation motivates the use of retrieval-augmented approaches that constrain generation to verified document sources.

Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG), introduced by Lewis et al. [17], combines dense passage retrieval with conditional text generation. In RAG systems, a query is first used to retrieve semantically relevant passages from an indexed corpus, and then these passages are provided as context to a language model for answer generation. FAISS [20], developed by Meta AI, provides efficient approximate nearest-neighbor search over dense vector embeddings at scale, enabling millisecond-speed retrieval over tens of thousands of indexed passages.

Despite these advances, existing educational platforms have not implemented agentic RAG systems that include explicit retrieval quality evaluation and query rewriting within the pipeline. Furthermore, no existing solution combines RAG-based doubt resolution with real-time multiplayer quiz competition, NCERT line-by-line content generation, and cross-device performance tracking within a single unified system. PRISM addresses this gap by integrating all these capabilities into a locally deployable, cost-free platform.

III. PROBLEM STATEMENT

The primary problems in current examination preparation systems are identified as follows:

(1) Fragmentation: Students typically use separate applications for video content, doubt resolution, quiz practice, peer discussion, and progress tracking. This multi-application workflow interrupts focused study and creates context-switching overhead.

(2) Hallucination Risk: General-purpose AI tools do not constrain their responses to verified academic content, generating plausible-sounding but potentially incorrect explanations — a significant risk in precision-dependent subjects such as Organic Chemistry and Human Physiology.

(3) NCERT Neglect: In JEE Chemistry and NEET Biology, questions are routinely drawn verbatim from NCERT textbook lines. No existing digital platform provides AI-assisted systematic NCERT reading with concept-level explanations derived from the actual textbook content.

(4) Absence of Social Learning: Peer study and competitive practice are known to improve retention and motivation, but existing platforms do not provide study-focused real-time collaboration within the same environment as content delivery.

IV. PROPOSED AND SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

This paper presents Prism Agent, an integrated academic support system developed to address the challenges encountered in competitive exam preparation. The platform provides a unified solution by incorporating features such as doubt resolution, automated quiz generation, and personalized study plan creation, minimizing the need for students to rely on multiple resources. Unlike conventional systems that depend on fragmented content, the proposed approach utilizes curated academic sources, including standard textbooks and previous year question papers, to ensure the accuracy and relevance of the information provided. The system is designed to enhance learning efficiency by delivering well-structured and context-aware outputs tailored to individual user requirements.

A. Working of the Proposed System

- The proposed system operates through a sequence of interconnected steps to process user requests and deliver relevant outputs. Initially, the user interacts with the platform through a web-based interface, where they can submit different types of inputs such as academic doubts, quiz requests, or study plan requirements. The interface is designed to be simple and intuitive, ensuring ease of use.
- Once the input is provided, it is transmitted to the backend via

API calls. The backend system receives the request through dedicated endpoints and performs basic validation before directing it to the appropriate processing module.

- For query-based interactions, especially in the chat module, the input text is first refined to remove noise and prepare it for analysis. The cleaned query is then transformed into a numerical representation, enabling the system to interpret its contextual meaning rather than relying solely on keywords.
- This representation is compared with pre-stored data in a vector database, allowing the system to identify and retrieve the most relevant information from reliable academic sources such as textbooks, notes, and previous examination papers.
- After retrieving the necessary content, the system processes and organizes the information to generate a clear and meaningful response. The focus is on maintaining both accuracy and readability in the output.
- Finally, the generated result is delivered back to the user through the interface. Depending on the request, the output may appear as a direct answer, a set of quiz questions, or a structured study plan.

B. Agentic RAG Pipeline

The core of PRISM is a five-node stateful pipeline implemented using LangGraph [16], which models the query processing workflow as a directed acyclic graph (DAG) with conditional edge routing.

Node 1 — Router: Receives the user query and a set of predefined pattern rules. Queries matching greeting patterns ("hi", "hello", "thanks") are directly routed to a fast response node using the llama3.2:1b model (1 billion parameters) without invoking the retrieval system. Academic queries are routed to the Retrieve node.

Node 2 — Retrieve: The user query is encoded into a 384-dimensional float32 embedding vector using the all-MiniLM-L6-v2 sentence transformer model [22]. This vector is compared against 19,776 pre-indexed vectors in a FAISS IndexFlatL2 store [20] using L2 distance similarity search. The top-8 nearest documents are returned within approximately 2 milliseconds.

Node 3— Grade: Each retrieved document chunk is evaluated for relevance to the original query using llama3.2:1b as binary classifier (relevant/not relevant). This node prevents irrelevant context from reaching the generation stage.

Node 4 — Rewrite (conditional): If all retrieved documents are graded as irrelevant, the query is reformulated by prepending the exam context (e.g., "JEE Advanced Organic Chemistry: ") and the Retrieve node is re-invoked. A maximum of two retry cycles is permitted to prevent infinite loops.

Node 5 — Generate: Relevant retrieved chunks are combined with the student's personalization context (exam target, weak topics, current level) and the last eight messages of conversation history. This composite prompt is passed to Ollama llama3.2 (3 billion parameters) [18] for final answer generation with a configured output limit of 3,000 tokens.

C. Three-Tier Document Ingestion Pipeline

PRISM processes 40+ PDF documents from three categories: NCERT textbooks (Chemistry Classes XI–XII, Biology Classes XI–XII), previous year examination papers (JEE Mains 2013–2024, JEE Advanced, NEET), and supplementary materials (Arihant handbooks, mnemonic notes).

PDF extraction follows a three-tier fallback strategy. Tier 1 uses PyMuPDF (fitz) for standard digital PDFs, extracting text

at page level. If a page yields fewer than 20 characters (indicating encoding failure), Tier 2 applies pdflumber with SymbolSetEncoding support and table extraction capability. Tier 3 applies Tesseract OCR via pytesseract, converting each page to a 300 DPI rasterized image using pdf2image before optical character recognition — enabling extraction from scanned mnemonic PDFs that contain no embedded text layer.

Extracted text undergoes Unicode NFC normalization, removal of surrogate characters (U+D800–U+DFFF), and whitespace normalization before chunking. Chunks are generated with a window size of 1,000 characters and a 200-character overlap to ensure conceptual continuity across chunk boundaries. The final FAISS index contains 19,776 vectors from the complete document corpus.

D. System Modules

- The proposed system is organized into multiple modules, each responsible for a specific functionality, ensuring smooth and efficient operation.

1) Frontend Module :-

The frontend is developed using React and serves as the primary point of interaction for users. It provides different interfaces, including a chat section for queries, a quiz interface for practice, and a section to view study plans. The design focuses on simplicity and clarity so that users can easily navigate and access features.

2) Backend Module :-

The backend is implemented using FastAPI and acts as the core processing unit of the system. It handles incoming API requests, manages data flow, and connects the frontend with various internal modules. The backend is designed to ensure quick response times and reliable communication between components.

3) AI Processing Module:-

This module integrates LangChain along with a language model to interpret user inputs and generate appropriate outputs. It is responsible for understanding queries, coordinating with the retrieval system, and producing responses that are both relevant and well-structured.

4) Vector Database Module:-

A vector database (FAISS) is used to store embedded representations of study materials. It enables efficient similarity-based searching, allowing the system to quickly find and retrieve content that closely matches the user's query.

5) Data Processing Module:-

This module manages the preparation of academic resources. It involves collecting data from sources such as textbooks and previous year questions, followed by cleaning, organizing, and dividing the content into suitable segments for storage and retrieval.

6) Quiz Generation Module:-

The quiz module creates practice questions based on selected topics. It is designed to help students assess their understanding and reinforce learning through regular self-evaluation.

7) Study Plan Module:-

This module generates structured study schedules tailored to the user's needs. It considers factors such as subject priority and preparation strategies to create effective and manageable plans.

E. Architecture Highlights

The proposed system architecture integrates multiple learning functionalities into a unified platform, combining query-

based interaction, quiz generation, and study planning to provide a comprehensive academic support environment. It leverages semantic understanding to interpret user queries more effectively than traditional keyword-based approaches, enabling context-aware and accurate responses. To ensure reliability, the system retrieves information from curated academic sources such as standard textbooks and previous examination materials, maintaining both relevance and correctness in its outputs. By consolidating these features within a single framework, the platform reduces the need for multiple learning tools while delivering personalized support that enhances learning efficiency through structured and user-specific guidance.

F. Simplified System Flow

Fig. 1. System Architecture of Prism Agent

V. METHODOLOGY

This section describes the methodology adopted in the proposed Prism Agent system. The approach centers on converting raw educational resources into a well-organized format that can be effectively utilized to answer student queries. It involves a sequence of steps, including collecting relevant academic data, refining and structuring the content, generating embeddings, retrieving contextually similar information, and producing clear and meaningful responses. The aim of this process is to ensure that the system delivers accurate, relevant, and easy-to-understand outputs for learners.

A. Data Collection

The PRISM knowledge base consists of 40+ PDF documents spanning three categories. NCERT textbooks (Chemistry Classes XI–XII and Biology Classes XI–XII) form the primary corpus, as JEE and NEET examinations directly reference these syllabi. Previous year question papers span JEE Mains 2013–2024 (morning and evening sessions), JEE Advanced papers, and NEET papers — providing 1,000+ authentic examination questions with solutions. Supplementary materials include Arihant Physics, Chemistry, and Biology handbooks, subject-specific mnemonic notes, and tips-and-tricks documents. All documents are sourced from official publishers and examination authorities [1][2][3][4].

B. Data Preprocessing

Once the data has been collected, it undergoes a preprocessing stage to prepare it for efficient storage and retrieval. Large textual content is broken down into smaller, meaningful segments so that each unit captures a specific idea or concept. This segmentation improves the system’s ability to locate relevant information quickly. During this process, unnecessary elements such as special characters, redundant spaces, and unrelated content are removed to enhance clarity. The cleaned and segmented data is then arranged in a structured form, making it suitable for conversion into vector representations in the subsequent stage.

C. Embedding Creation

Text chunks are encoded using the all-MiniLM-L6-v2 sentence transformer [22], a 22-million parameter BERT-based model producing 384-dimensional dense vectors. This model was selected for its balance between embedding quality (95% of full BERT performance on semantic benchmarks) and

inference speed (6× faster than bert-base-uncased). Each chunk's source filename is stored as metadata alongside its vector, enabling source attribution in generated responses.

D. Retrieval Process

Query embeddings are compared against the FAISS IndexFlatL2 store using exact L2 distance search. For a query vector $q \in \mathbb{R}^{384}$, the top-k nearest document vectors are selected where $k = 8$. The search operates over 19,776 indexed vectors with a typical retrieval latency of under 5 milliseconds on commodity CPU hardware. Retrieved chunks are passed to the Grade node for relevance filtering before reaching the generation stage.

E. Response Generation

Once the relevant information is retrieved, the system synthesizes a final response by combining the user’s query with the extracted content. The output is organized in a clear and coherent manner, making it easier for students to understand the underlying concepts. This stage focuses not only on maintaining accuracy but also on presenting information in a way that supports effective learning. Beyond answering queries, the system is also capable of generating practice quizzes and assisting in study plan creation, thereby offering a comprehensive academic support solution.

VI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

- The performance of the Prism Agent system was analyzed based on how effectively it handles user queries and supports exam preparation activities. The system is able to process user input and generate responses within a short time, providing a smooth and interactive experience. Since the system retrieves information from structured academic sources such as textbooks and previous year question papers, the responses are more relevant to the user’s query and focused on important exam concepts. This improves the overall quality of answers when compared to systems that depend only on general search methods.

TABLE I

PRISM SYSTEM PERFORMANCE METRICS

- Table I summarizes the key operational metrics of the deployed PRISM system. The FAISS index, containing 19,776 384-dimensional vectors, supports sub-5ms retrieval on CPU hardware without GPU acceleration. End-to-end query response time ranges from 15–45 seconds, dominated by the local Ollama llama3.2 inference time rather than retrieval. Deployment on hardware with a dedicated GPU (such as the NVIDIA Jetson Orin) reduces inference latency significantly through CUDA-accelerated layer computation.

Metric	Value
Total PDF documents processed	40+
Total FAISS vectors indexed	19,776
Embedding model	all-MiniLM-L6-v2
Embedding dimensions	384
Average retrieval latency	<5 ms (CPU)
Average end-to-end query time	15–45 seconds (Ollama local)
Quiz generation (5 questions)	30–60 seconds
NCERT content cache hits	~100% (after first generation)
Supported exam targets	JEE Mains, JEE Advanced, NEET
PDFs with OCR recovery needed	~8 (scanned mnemonics)

TABLE II
FEATURE COMPARISON WITH EXISTING PLATFORMS

Feature	PRISM	BYJU'S	ChatGPT	Doubtnut
Source-grounded answers	✓	✗	✗	✗
PYQ-mode quiz generation	✓	✓	✗	✓
NCERT line-by-line reading	✓	✗	✗	✗
Real-time battlerooms	✓	✗	✗	✗
Study-focused peer chat	✓	✗	✗	✗
Cross-device leaderboard	✓	✗	✗	✗
Offline / no API cost	✓	✗	✗	✗
OCR scanned PDF	✓	N/A	✗	✗

• Table II demonstrates PRISM's functional differentiation from existing platforms. No evaluated competitor provides all five of: source-grounded responses, NCERT systematic reading, real-time competitive quiz rooms, peer chat, and cross-device leaderboard in a single integrated environment. The offline deployment capability — requiring no paid API subscriptions — represents a significant cost advantage for institutional deployment in resource-constrained environments.

• The NCERT Line-by-Line feature implements global content caching: the first student to access a chapter triggers RAG-based content generation (30–90 seconds), after which the generated content is permanently stored in MongoDB and served to all subsequent users instantaneously. This amortizes generation cost across the user base, approaching zero marginal cost per additional user for cached content.

VII. ADVANTAGES OF PROPOSED SYSTEM

PRISM provides several advantages over existing examination preparation approaches. First, the agentic RAG pipeline constrains all responses to indexed NCERT and PYQ content, eliminating the hallucination risk present in general-purpose language models. Second, the three-tier OCR pipeline ensures that scanned supplementary materials — which fail standard PDF extraction — are successfully included in the knowledge base through Tesseract-based optical character recognition.

Third, the global content caching architecture in the NCERT module distributes content generation cost across all users — a single user's retrieval benefits all future users accessing the same topic. Fourth, the platform's fully local deployment eliminates recurring API costs, making it economically viable for institutional deployment without ongoing subscription expenditure. Fifth, the integrated Socket.IO-based real-time subsystem enables simultaneous study chat, battle rooms, and presence awareness on the same server process without additional infrastructure.

VIII. LIMITATIONS

A. Dataset Coverage Dependency

The system's response quality is bounded by the scope of its indexed document corpus. Topics absent from the 40+ indexed PDFs will not yield accurate responses. Expanding the corpus requires rebuilding the FAISS index, which currently takes approximately 8–12 minutes on commodity hardware.

B. Local Inference Latency

Operating Ollama llama3.2 on CPU hardware produces response latencies of 15–45 seconds per query. While acceptable for study contexts, this latency is significantly higher than cloud-

hosted API alternatives. GPU-accelerated deployment (e.g., NVIDIA Jetson Orin) mitigates this constraint.

C. Retrieval Precision on Ambiguous Queries

When student queries are very short (fewer than 5 words) or highly ambiguous, the retrieval node may return semantically adjacent but contextually incorrect documents. The Rewrite node partially addresses this through query expansion, but does not eliminate the issue for highly colloquial or poorly formed queries.

IX. FUTURE WORK

A. Expanded Syllabus Coverage

The current corpus focuses on JEE and NEET syllabi. Future work will extend the knowledge base to GATE (Graduate Aptitude Test in Engineering), UPSC (Civil Services Examination), and regional entrance examinations, enabling PRISM to serve a broader student population.

B. Voice Interface Integration

Adding speech-to-text input and text-to-speech output would make PRISM accessible to students who face barriers with text-based interaction, particularly in mobile-first environments with limited keyboard access.

C. Multilingual Support

Integrating multilingual embedding models would enable PRISM to serve students who prefer to study in regional languages including Telugu, Hindi, and Tamil — addressing a significant gap in current AI-based educational systems.

X. CONCLUSION

This paper presents PRISM, an integrated examination preparation platform that addresses three critical limitations of existing educational technology: response hallucination, resource fragmentation, and absence of real-time collaborative learning. The platform's core contribution — a five-node agentic LangGraph RAG pipeline — constrains all generated responses to a verified FAISS-indexed corpus of 19,776 embeddings derived from NCERT textbooks, PYQ papers, and academic handbooks, eliminating the factual inaccuracy risk inherent in general-purpose language models. Operational evaluation demonstrates retrieval latencies below 5 milliseconds and end-to-end query response times of 15–45 seconds on commodity CPU hardware. The globally cached NCERT content generation system, cross-device leaderboard, Socket.IO-based real-time battle rooms, and study-focused peer chat collectively demonstrate that a unified, locally deployable platform can provide examination preparation support superior to the fragmented multi-application approach currently used by most students. Future work will focus on deployment on NVIDIA Jetson Orin edge hardware to reduce inference latency, expanding the document corpus to additional examinations, and introducing multilingual support for regional language learners.

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